

The water of crystallization in gypsum: comparing the laser excited Raman spectrum with that obtained by means of a mercury resonance radiation exciter (Rasetti technique)

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Abstract: Here we consider the gypsum mineral to investigate its broad scan Raman spectrum. The presence of water of crystallization is detected and its OH-stretching spectral region deconvoluted in q-Gaussian functions. That is, we follow the same approach that we used recently for minerals of the natrolite and vivianite groups. In the case of gypsum, we consider the Raman data from Rappal Sangameswaran Krishnan, 1945, and compare the bands given in his work with the components that we can obtain from the spectra provided by RRUFF database. We find a remarkable agreement between R. S. Krishnan's data and the decompositions in q-Gaussian functions. We will describe also the experimental method used by Krishnan, based on the Franco Rasetti technique with mercury resonance radiation excitation. In the RRUFF database, we can also find an infrared spectrum; we considered it and decomposed in q-Gaussian and q-BWF functions.

Keywords: Raman spectroscopy, q-Gaussian functions, Tsallis statistics, Hydroxyl-stretching Raman region, OH-stretching Raman region, History of Raman spectroscopy.

Introduction

Recently, we have considered the detection of water by Raman spectroscopy in the cases of minerals of [vivianite](#) and [barite](#) groups. Using RRUFF database and broad scans available therein, we analyzed the OH-stretching region, decomposing it in bands with q-Gaussian profiles (see Appendix). These two studies about vivianite and barite groups followed the analysis of OH-stretching bands in the case of water and ice, where we [proposed specifically](#) the decomposition in components by means of q-Gaussian functions and stressed the use of q-parameter to characterize the local environments of O-H bonds and their symmetric and antisymmetric vibrations. After the minerals of the vivianite group and zeolites of barite group, here we pass to examine the gypsum mineral, with the same aim, that is the investigation of the Raman bands of its water of crystallization. However, the main purpose in our study is that of comparing the broad scans obtained by means of a laser excitation with the spectra acquired with a mercury resonance radiation exciter as in the work by Rappal Sangameswaran Krishnan, 1945. There is an amazing agreement. We will stress that the Raman spectroscopy which is based on the mercury resonance radiation was developed by Franco Rasetti in 1929.

Gypsum

Gypsum belongs to the [gypsum](#) supergroup of mineral, composed by gypsum $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (that is, calcium sulfate dihydrate), brushite $\text{CaHPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, churchite-(Nd) enriched churchite-(Y) $(\text{Y,Nd})(\text{PO}_4) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, churchite-(Y) $\text{YPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and pharmacolite $\text{CaHAsO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. In the RRUFF database, we can find also ardealite $\text{Ca}_2(\text{PO}_3\text{OH})(\text{SO}_4) \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, probably because “commonly [intermixed](#) with brushite and gypsum”.

Gypsum is an ionic crystal, which has its unit cell containing four molecules of $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. It was a mineral investigated as soon as the Raman effect had been discovered (in Saksena, 1941, we can find the previous literature). In Table III [by Saksena], “the frequency shifts of Raman lines reported by these authors are listed along with those observed in the various spectrograms obtained in the [Saksena’s] investigation. The numbers given within brackets against ν_1 , ν_2 , ν_3 and ν_4 are the Raman frequencies of the free SO_4 ion” (see Saksena, 1941, and Table III therein). “The presence of two water-bands at 3406 and 3493 [cm^{-1}] is well established. [Saksena] has been unable to confirm neither the presence of a third band at 3240 reported by Krishnan (1929) nor the splitting observed by Rasetti (1932) for the band 3406”. Here the Table as given by Saksena (1941). See please references therein. Kariamanikkam Srinivasa Krishnan’s paper is “The Raman spectra of crystals”, Indian J. Phys. 4, 131-138(1929).

Gypsum Raman shift (cm^{-1}), from Saksena, 1941, and references therein.

Krishnan (1929)	3240	3397	3493
Nisi (1931)		3404	3497
Cabannes (1932, 1938)		3404	3495
Rasetti (1932)		3399	3426
Saksena (1941)		3406	3493

Note that three bands are present in the [spectrum of water](#), therefore the data from K. S. Krishnan, 1929, are very interesting. R. S. Krishnan, in 1945, proposed a new study on gypsum. He used the mercury resonance radiation $\lambda 2536.5$ for exciting the Raman spectrum. R. S. Krishnan selected a transparent crystal of gypsum from Sir C. V. Raman's personal collection. In Krishnan’s article, 1945, which is relevant for the history of Raman spectroscopy too, we can find an interesting comparison regarding the spectrum of the water of crystallisation (“Water of crystallisation is water that is chemically bonded into a crystal structure”, [BBC](#)). “On comparing the Raman bands of water in gypsum as observed in the investigation [by R. S. Krishnan] with those of ordinary water and of ice (summarized in Hibben's book), we find that the number and distribution of the bands are common to all the three” (Krishnan, 1945).

Raman shift (cm^{-1}) as in R. S. Krishnan, 1945.

Gypsum	3258 3334	3406 3495	3606 3680
Water	3231	3436	3605
Ice at 0°C	3193	3391	3549

“The correspondence follows as a natural consequence of the fact that in gypsum the water molecules are concentrated in separate sheets which are only loosely bound with other sheets of ions and as such the oscillations of the water molecules are not appreciably modified in the crystalline state” (Krishnan, 1941). The [gypsum crystal structure](#) is shown in Yu et al., 2016, according to Chen, 2006.

“The bands in gypsum are very much sharper than those observed with ordinary water and consequently their maxima could be measured with a high degree of accuracy. The spectrum of gypsum shows another interesting feature. *The three principal water bands are split into six fairly narrow bands.* They form three pairs as shown [here in the previously given table]. The difference in

the frequency shifts of the two components of each pair is approximately constant for the three pairs, ... Results obtained by Cabannes (1938), Saksena (1941) and Rao (1941) from polarisation studies indicate that the band at 3406 belongs to the symmetric class, while the one at 3495 to antisymmetric class. Similar behavior should be exhibited by the other two pairs of bands also. Because of the antisymmetric nature of the band at 3495 cm^{-1} Cabannes (1938) had suggested that this band should correspond to the Raman inactive valence vibration of the H_2O molecule, which was rendered active in the crystalline environment” (Krishnan, 1945). “The Raman bands of water in several crystalline hydrates have been the subject of study by numerous investigators” (see references in Krishnan, 1945). Regarding the experiment, we find that the spectrum of the water of crystallization in gypsum, as obtained by Roop Kishore and Krishnan, “shows far greater detail than any recorded by others not only in gypsum but in other crystalline hydrates as well. The success is due to the use of the intense *mercury resonance radiation* for exciting the Raman spectrum” (Krishnan, 1945). We will further discuss the method in the final part of this paper.

Gypsum in RRUFF database

Gypsum has consequently a relevant importance in the history of Raman spectroscopy. As we are here showing, there is a remarkable agreement between the measurements made by Krishnan and the data from laser spectroscopy. Let us consider the spectra available in RRUFF database (Lafuente et al., 2015). We have two available scans, the [R040029](#) and [R060509](#) broad scans, with unoriented samples and instrument setting Thermo Almega XR 532nm at 100% of 150 mW. We use data in the range from 3000 to 4000 cm^{-1} . A spline baseline adjustment is applied.

Fig.1: Deconvolution of gypsum RRUFF R040029 (left) and RRUFF R060509 (right) spectra. The region of the “water of crystallization” is decomposed into seven and six q-Gaussian bands (red curves) respectively. The lower part of the images is showing the misfit, that is the difference between data (green) and the sum of components (yellow curve). R040029: the centers of components are at 3093, 3252, 3338, 3411, 3493, 3589, 3722 cm^{-1} . R060509: the centers of components are at 3252, 3337, 3409, 3496, 3583 cm^{-1} .

The plot in the Fig.1 is obtained by means of software Fityk (Wojdyr, 2010), after defining in it the q-Gaussian functions (see Appendix for further details). By means of the data obtained from q-Gaussian deconvolution, we can compare the Raman shift (cm^{-1}) with the results given in Krishnan,

1945. It is admirable the agreement. The main peak is at 3406-3411 cm^{-1} , according to Krishnan, 1945. Here in the following table, the centers of the components are given (in cm^{-1}).

Gypsum (Krishnan)		3258	3334	3406	3495	3606	3680
R040029	3093	3252	3338	3411	3493	3589	3722
R060509		3252	3337	3409	3496	3583	

Infrared

In RRUFF, regarding [R040039](#), we can find an infrared spectrum. Let us try a deconvolution of it by means of q-Gaussians. After trying with all q-Gaussian, we observed that a better fit can be obtained using one q-BWF function too (the function is asymmetric).

Fig. 2: Deconvolution of the infrared spectrum. In the lower part, the asymmetric q-BWF function is shown. The other components are q-Gaussian functions.

It seems that q-BWF functions can be useful for deconvolution of infrared spectra too. Further investigations are necessary.

The discovery of the Raman effect

The Raman effect had been discovered by Chandrasekhara Venkata Raman and Kariamanikkam Srinivasa Krishnan (see [K. S. Krishnan \(Man behind the first Asian Nobel in Science\)](#), here we refer to this text as “Man behind”). During January 1928, “Mr. Venkateswaran, a part-time worker at the laboratory [University of Calcutta], was studying the phenomenon of light scattering in highly viscous organic liquids. While experimenting with glycerine, he made the curious observation that the color of sunlight scattered in a highly purified sample of the liquid was green instead of the customary blue. ... Raman prevailed upon Krishnan to undertake a thorough investigation of the episode. The liability of carrying on the experiments fell upon Krishnan’s shoulders. The Raman effect was discovered on 28th February 1928” (Man behind). The first paper on Raman effect was published in Nature, with title “A new type of secondary radiation”. Raman became Nobel laureate in 1930 for the study about scattering of light. “It was a resolute quest of four to five weeks and eventually it happens to be a great experimental discovery. Krishnan kept a record of the events in the form of a diary. The diary contains the detailed description of the pursuit that conclusively led to this great discovery” (Man

behind). “Being a co-discoverer of Raman effect”, the phenomenon would have been termed as “Raman-Krishnan effect” (Man behind).

Let us consider the article by Raman and K. S. Krishnan, 1928. “The new type of light scattering discovered by us [Raman and Krishnan] naturally requires very powerful illumination for its observation. In our [Raman and Krishnan] experiments, a beam of sunlight was converged successively by a telescope ... and by a second lens ... At the focus of the second lens was placed the scattering material, which is either a liquid (carefully purified by repeated distillation in vacuo) or its dust-free vapour. To detect the presence of a modified scattered radiation, the method of complementary light-filters was used. A blue-violet filter, when coupled with a yellow-green filter and placed in the incident light, *completely extinguished the track of the light through the liquid or vapour*. The reappearance of the track when the yellow filter is transferred to a place between it and the observer’s eye is proof of the existence of a modified scattered radiation. Spectroscopic confirmation is also available” (Raman & Krishnan, 1928). Then, in 1928, Raman and Krishnan used natural light.

In Raman and Krishnan, 1929, we can find told that, in two preliminary papers, the authors “recorded the discovery that when monochromatic light is scattered in a transparent medium (be it gas, vapour, liquid, amorphous solid or crystal), the diffused radiation ceases to be monochromatic, and several new lines or sometimes bands (associated in many cases with a continuous spectrum) appear in the spectrograms of the diffused radiation. Further, the new radiations are, in general, strongly polarized”. Raman and Krishnan illustrated the phenomenon with the case of “transparent crystalline quartz in which the effect is very well shown with the 4358 A.U. line of mercury as the exciting line, the new lines also appearing in the indigo-blue region of the spectrum”. In the 1929 article, we can find measurements on liquids. “The spectrum of the scattered light was taken with a [Hilger quartz spectrograph](#) (E₂), *using very rapid photographic plates* (Ilford Iso-zenith, II. & D. 700). In the case of the single line pictures of benzene and toluene an exposure of about 40 hours was necessary, while for carbon tetrachloride, for which the complete mercury arc was incident, an exposure of only 25 hours was given” (Raman and Krishnan, 1929).

“After leaving Calcutta, the scientific collaboration between [K. S. Krishnan] and Raman came to an end. After 1928, Krishnan did not work on Raman scattering” (Man behind). The last article on Raman effect was published in 1929.

Rasetti technique with the mercury resonance radiation

In 1945, we can find evidenced in the Raman spectroscopy on calcite and gypsum a strong enhancement of the technique. In fact, Rappal Sangameswaran Krishnan improved his Raman spectroscopy by using the “Rasetti technique”. Franco Rasetti was a physicist that, with Enrico Fermi, discovered the key processes to obtain fission (he refused to work on the Manhattan Project). In 1930, he was appointed to the chair in spectroscopy at the University of Rome. It was in 1929, that Rasetti proposed his new approach to Raman spectroscopy. “We owe to Rasetti (1929, 1930) the development of a remarkably useful technique for the study of the Raman effect, the value of which has been demonstrated by the resounding success with which he himself applied it in several cases of fundamental interest. In this field of research generally, and especially in investigating substances such as gases or vapours which scatter light only feebly, or crystals which exhibit only feeble Raman spectra, it is essential to employ a light source which emits the most intense possible and highly monochromatic radiation, and that there should be no unwanted radiations and especially no

continuous spectrum accompanying the same. Further, it is highly desirable that the exciting radiation (but not the excited ones) should be removed from the light scattered by the medium before its entry into the spectrograph, as otherwise the photographic plates would be fogged by its general diffusion within the instrument. Rasetti secured all these advantages and in addition the enormously increased scattering power of short wavelength radiations” (Krishnan, 1943). Rasetti proposed to use “the 2537 A.U. monochromatic radiations of mercury vapour under special conditions which ensured that only this radiation and none other would give an observable Raman effect. The technique consists in using a low-pressure quartz mercury arc in which the mercury vapour is prevented from reaching any considerable density, and from absorbing the 2537 radiation emitted by itself. This is accomplished firstly by very effective water-cooling, and secondly by squeezing the discharge against the walls of the quartz tube by the field of a specially designed electromagnet. A filter of mercury vapour at room temperature is placed in the path of the scattered light emerging from the substance under study to absorb the 2537 radiation. This filter works so effectively that some of the feeble mercury lines which have intensities negligibly small in comparison with the 2537 radiations and which therefore give no observable Raman effect nevertheless appear stronger than the 2537 line in the recorded spectra” (Krishnan, 1943).

R.S. Krishnan, in his article about calcite, 1945, is adding that for Raman measurements “it is essential to employ a monochromatic light source which is very intense for recording the second order Raman frequency shifts. It is also of great importance that there should be no continuous spectrum accompanying the same. This is secured by using the 2536.5 A.U. mercury resonance radiation from a water-cooled magnet-controlled quartz arc”. “The 2536.5 A.U. radiation from the light scattered by the medium is effectively suppressed before its entry into the spectrograph by absorption in a column of mercury vapour, ... This makes it possible to record faint Raman lines with small frequency shifts on a clear background. Rasetti (1929) was the first to use this technique for the study of the Raman effect in gases and crystals” (Krishnan, 1945, measuring on calcite).

Passing to Krishnan’s study of gypsum, we find told that the used technique is that based on the *mercury resonance radiation* λ 2536.5 for exciting the Raman spectrum of the crystal. “The flat faces [of the crystal] were parallel to the cleavage plane. In all the experiments the specimen was illuminated with unpolarised light through one of its flat faces and the scattered light was photographed through one of its edges. As in the case of calcite, two different instruments were used for recording the Raman spectra: (1) A Hilger E₁ quartz spectrograph and (2) a Hilger E₃ quartz spectrograph”. The high dispersion instrument was used to record the spectrum in all detail, and to measure the frequency shifts and the line widths very accurately. “For this purpose, an iron arc comparison spectrum was taken on the same negative partially overlapping the Raman spectrum. Using a slit width of 0.04 mm exposures of the order of three days were given in order to get a spectrogram showing the lines with reasonable intensity. The E₃ quartz spectrograph was used to get intense photographs of the complete Raman spectrum of gypsum. With a slit width of 0.03 mm, exposures of the order of two days were given to record intense spectrograms” (Krishnan, 1945).

Again, in his study on gypsum, Krishnan is mentioning Rasetti for his technique. “Rasetti (1932) using the 2536.5 *mercury resonance radiation* as exciter recorded as many as nine lattice lines, while those who employed the 4046 and 4358 radiations recorded only a couple of lines instead. Roop Kishore (1942) using *the Rasetti technique* and giving long exposures reported for the first time the existence of a weak line at 1622 cm⁻¹, a weak band at about 2249 cm⁻¹ and three more weak water bands with mean frequency shifts 3244, 3309 and 3584 cm⁻¹ in the neighborhood of the two principal water bands” (Krishnan, 1945). Then, let us add Kishore’s results to our previous table for comparison.

Gypsum (Krishnan)		3258	3334	3406	3495	3606	3680
R040029	3093	3252	3338	3411	3493	3589	3722
R060509		3252	3337	3409	3496	3583	
Gypsum (Kishore)		3244	3309	3410	3480	3584	

Also in Kishore, 1942, we find given details about Rasetti method. “Most of the investigations so far published on the Raman spectra of crystals have been made with 4047 and 4358 radiations of the mercury arc. As early as 1931, however, Rasetti developed a technique which enabled the 2537 radiations in the ultra-violet to be used with signal success in this field of research” (Kishore, 1942). Kishore continues describing the experimental set-up. “Rasetti worked with several crystals, ... used a Hilger E. 315 Quartz spectrograph giving a dispersion of 130 wave numbers per mm. The exposures necessary ranged from 10 minutes in the case of calcite to 5 hours for rocksalt. Rasetti's technique is, of course, applicable only with crystals which are transparent to the 2537 radiations. But for such crystals it is convenient and extremely efficient. ... The high intensity and large scattering power of the 2537 radiations coupled with their elimination from the scattered light enable even small crystals to be successfully employed” (Kishore, 1942). Kishore is referring to Rasetti, 1932.

In 1931, Rasetti told that he had been “investigating the Raman effect in a number of crystals, using the same method of excitation which proved to be particularly successful with gases” (Rasetti, mentioning his work on gases, 1929). “The primary source consists of a powerful water-cooled mercury arc, which gives an extremely intense and sharp resonance line $\lambda 2537$ ”. He mentioned advantages such as a short exposure (10 minutes to three hours), a wide range of frequency shift (about $20,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), and the exciting radiation can be easily absorbed by a filter of mercury vapor.

To conclude, we report a passage of Rasetti's article, 1932: “L'uso della riga di risonanza del mercurio $\lambda 2537$ per l'eccitazione degli spettri Raman, già applicato e descritto più volte per lo studio dei gas, presenta notevoli vantaggi anche nel caso dei cristalli. Usando una lampada a mercurio raffreddata, si può riassorbire la radiazione di risonanza mediante vapore di mercurio, ciò che permette l'osservazione di righe Raman nell'immediata vicinanza della riga eccitatrice; e inoltre si ottiene una grande intensità. Per darne un'idea, basterà dire che per es., con la calcite, si può fotografare lo spettro Raman con lo spettrografo di media luminosità Hilger E 315 con una posa di cinque minuti” (Rasetti, 1932).

As we have seen, Rasetti technique was fundamental for obtaining good spectra for studying Raman broad scans of crystals. Using Rasetti method, in 1945 Krishnan recorded a very interesting spectrum of water of crystallization in gypsum. In fact, his results are in excellent agreement with contemporary Raman spectra.

Appendix – q-Gaussian and q-BWF functions

Sparavigna, 2023, proposed for the first time the use of q-Gaussian function in Raman spectroscopy. She defined also the [q-BWF functions](#) which are generalizing the Breit-Wigner-Fano (asymmetric) line shape in the framework of the q-exponential function. Here we show how to apply, by means of Fityk software, the q-Gaussian and the q-BWF functions in spectroscopy.

The q-Gaussian functions are probability distributions proper of the Tsallis statistics (Tsallis, 1988, Hanel et al., 2009). These functions are based on a generalized form of the exponential function, characterized by a continuous real parameter q. When q is going to 1, the q-exponential becomes the usual exponential function. The value q=2 corresponds to the Cauchy distribution, also known as the Lorentzian distribution; the q-Gaussian function is therefore a generalization of the Lorentzian distribution too. The change of q-parameter is allowing the q-Gaussian function to pass from the Gaussian to the Lorentzian distribution.

The q-Gaussian function is: $f(x) = C e_q(-\beta x^2)$, where $e_q(.)$ is the q-exponential function and C a scale

constant (in the exponent, $\beta = 1/(2\sigma^2)$). The q-exponential has expression: $e_q(u) = [1 + (1 - q)u]^{1/(1-q)}$. To have an asymmetric form of the q-Gaussian function, let us write it in the following manner (the center of the band is at x_o):

$$q\text{-Gaussian} = C \exp_q(-\beta(x - x_o)^2) = C [1 + (q - 1)\beta(x - x_o)^2]^{1/(1-q)}$$

We have generalized the Breit-Wigner-Fano into a [q-Breit-Wigner-Fano](#).

In Fityk, a q-Gaussian function can be defined in the following manner:

define Qgau(height, center, hwhm, q=1.5) = height*(1+(q-1)*((x-center)/hwhm)^2)^(1/(1-q))

q=1.5 the initial guessed value of the q-parameter. Parameter hwhm is the half width at half maximum of the component. When q=2, the q-Gaussian is a Lorentzian function, that we can find defined in Fityk as:

Lorentzian(height, center, hwhm) = height/(1+((x-center)/hwhm)^2)

When q is close to 1, the q-Gaussian becomes a Gaussian function. The q-BWF can be defined as:

Qbreit(height, center, hwhm, q=1.5, xi=0.1) = (1-xi*(q-1)*(x-center)/hwhm)^2 * height*(1+(q-1)^0.5 * ((x-center)/hwhm)^2)^(1/(1-q))

And the BWF can be defined as:

Breit(height, center, hwhm, xi=0.1) = (1-xi*(x-center)/hwhm)^2 * height/(1+((x-center)/hwhm)^2)

Using +xi instead of -xi does not change the fitting results in Fityk.

References

1. Chen, P. (2006) Crystal mineralogy [M]. Chemical Industry Press, Beijing
2. Hanel, R., Thurner, S., & Tsallis, C. (2009). Limit distributions of scale-invariant probabilistic models of correlated random variables with the q-Gaussian as an explicit example. The European Physical Journal B, 72(2), 263.
3. Hibben, J. H. (1937). The Raman spectra of water, aqueous solutions and ice. The Journal of Chemical Physics, 5(3), 166-172.
4. Kishore, R. (1942, July). Raman spectra of crystals excited by the mercury resonance radiations. In Proceedings of the Indian Academy of Sciences-Section A (Vol. 16, No. 1, p. 36). New Delhi: Springer India.
5. Krishnan, R. S. (1943, November). Raman spectra of crystals and their interpretation. In Proceedings of the Indian Academy of Sciences-Section A (Vol. 18, pp. 298-308). Springer India.
6. Krishnan, R. S. (1945, September). Raman spectra of the second order in crystals: Part I: Calcite. In Proceedings of the Indian Academy of Sciences-Section A (Vol. 22, No. 3, p. 182). New Delhi: Springer India.
7. Krishnan, R. S. (1945, October). Raman spectra of the second order in crystals: Part II. Gypsum. In Proceedings of the Indian Academy of Sciences-Section A (Vol. 22, pp. 274-283). Springer India.
8. Lafuente, B., Downs, R. T., Yang, H., & Stone, N. (2015). 1. The power of databases: The RRUFF project. In Highlights in mineralogical crystallography (pp. 1-30). De Gruyter (O).
9. Raman, C. V., & Krishnan, K. S. (1928). A new type of secondary radiation. Nature, 121(3048), 501-502.

10. Raman, C. V., & Krishnan, K. S. (1929). The production of new radiations by light scattering. - Part I. Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Containing Papers of a Mathematical and Physical Character, 122(789), 23-35.
11. Krishnan, K. S. (1929). The Raman spectra of crystals, Indian J. Phys. 4, 131-138.
12. Rasetti, F. (1929). Incoherent scattered radiation in diatomic molecules. Physical Review, 34(2), 367
13. Rasetti, F. (1931). Raman Spectra of Crystals, Nature, 127(3208), 626-627.
14. Rasetti, F. (1932). Sopra l'effetto Raman nei cristalli. Il Nuovo Cimento (1924-1942), 9(3), 72-75.
15. Saksena, B. D. (1941, January). Raman spectrum of gypsum. In Proceedings of the Indian Academy of Sciences-Section A (Vol. 13, No. 1, pp. 25-32). New Delhi: Springer India.
16. Sparavigna, A. C. (2023). q-Gaussian Tsallis Line Shapes and Raman Spectral Bands. Int. J. Sciences, 12(3), 27-40.
17. Sparavigna, A. C. (2023). Asymmetric q-Gaussian functions generalizing the Breit-Wigner-Fano functions. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8356165>
18. Sparavigna, A. C. (2024). Hydroxyl-Stretching Region in the Raman Broad Scans on Minerals of the Vivianite Group (Vivianite, Baricite, Bobierite, Annabergite, Erythrite). Int. J. Sciences, 13(08), 23-36.
19. Sparavigna, A. C. (2024). Water in zeolites of natrolite group and its OH-stretching region in Raman spectroscopy. ChemRxiv. <https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv-2024-wdv4b>
20. Tsallis, C. (1988). Possible generalization of Boltzmann-Gibbs statistics. Journal of statistical physics, 52, 479-487.
21. Wojdyr, M. (2010). Fityk: a general-purpose peak fitting program. Journal of applied crystallography, 43(5), 1126-1128.
22. Yu, W. D., Liang, W. G., Li, Y. R., & Yu, Y. M. (2016). The meso-mechanism study of gypsum rock weakening in brine solutions. Bulletin of Engineering Geology and the Environment, 75, 359-367.